

POST OCCUPANCY EVALUATION OF BUILDING CONTEXT AND MASSING IN PUBLIC COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN NORTH-CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study was on post-occupancy evaluation of building context and massing in Public Colleges of Education North Central, Nigeria that were erected in the 60s - 80s with view to provide feedback and recommendations for improvement. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study was 933 drawn from the 13 public Colleges of Education (PCE) in North Central, Nigeria (NCN). The samples of the study were 420 respondents, 3 states, 6 colleges of education, being 45% respectively. The composition of the respondents comprised of 279 students, 135 lecturers and 6 architects purposively drawn from the 6 selected Departments of Technical Education, and works departments of the colleges. Six (6) lecture hall buildings were selected using stratified randomly sampling technique. Instrument for data collection was a 14 items structured questionnaire titled "Post Occupancy Evaluation of Building Context and Massing Questionnaire (POEBCM)". The questionnaire was administered using 6 trained research assistants. Two research questions and null hypotheses guided the study respectively. The reliability of the instrument was established at 0.87 using Cronbach Alpha. Descriptive statistical mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while ANOVA was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 levels of significance. The findings of the study among others revealed that, most of the college buildings did not suit the context of their surrounding environment. Similarly, on building massing, the study revealed among others that, viewing from the outside, the building parts did not integrate well with each other to form pleasant appearance. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations among others were made, that the lecture buildings be repositioned and be improved upon to blend with their surrounding environments. It was also suggested that the various parts of the buildings should be carefully remodelled to form a pleasant appearance unified structure.

Keywords: Post Occupancy Evaluation, Context and Massing

Introduction

A well designed completed building should function in the manner that will ensure users' satisfaction and as well facilitate educational process. Federal Government of Nigeria (2014) on Quality Assurance Curriculum Implementation Framework Policy for Colleges of Education (QACIPCE) stated that for quality education to emerge, there must be quality learning environment, and government would provide quality and adequate numbers of modern lecture buildings/theatres, social space arenas, and would continue to improve on the existing ones. By this development it is expected that the educational buildings available for whatever they are designed for would be from

time to time be improved upon, in order to fulfil their functional, technical and behavioural performance requirements.

Educational buildings are physical infrastructures and the built environments that accommodate other educational resources (Abisuga, 2013). Meanwhile, building context and massing are various building design features that their functions prove the performance ratings of buildings in use (Lavy, 2011). They form integral part of building design in this modern age. Building context addresses issue of new building development blending with built and natural features of the surrounding environment it is sited, while, massing involves the use of different shapes and sizes to form a unified structure creating a pleasant and harmonious appearance.

Over the years, building users are becoming more aware of the dangers associated with deteriorated educational buildings and related built environments with respects to lecturers and students' health and educational achievement. Cash (2019) observed that, when students are in poor educational buildings and related built environments, it means they are being placed in situation that will disadvantage them in their academic works and as well as wellbeing. Filardo (2018) in an assessment of developing nations' educational buildings observed that many developing countries' public educational buildings across the world today are faced with combined challenges of building deteriorating conditions and out-of-date design because of educational advancement, lack of regular building assessment and improvement needs among others. She recommended that, as educational programs advance, educational buildings should be improved upon as to meet up with the new developmental challenges.

Evidently to the above assertion, Abisuga (2013) and Ofide, Richard and Achuen (2015) in their separate research reports, observed that most buildings and built environments of most first and second generation public Universities, public colleges of education in North Central, Nigeria inclusive, are for one reason or the others in deplorable conditions and are no longer supporting, but frustrating educational process of this age. This development is in line with the observation of Aniebitabasi and Michael (2017) who stated that in Nigeria, buildings are rarely evaluated after built and handed over to the client. But Ezran (2020) posited that, the success and failure of building performance cannot be confirmed well without post occupancy evaluation. He recommended that building should be regularly improved upon using POE recommendations.

Statement of the Problem

There has been general out cried by members of public and evidently supported by several research reports that, most building elements and other built environments of 60s- 80s in public tertiary institutions in the North Central, Nigeria are poorly designed and constructed. Since their occupancy, no appropriate building assessments have been carried out on them for possible enhancement to actually meet the present educational needs and aspirations.

Evidently, to the above assertions, the researcher having visited few Public Colleges of Education in Benue and Plateau States observed that, some lecturers and students' complaint of poor buildings context and massing, and environmental unfriendliness. Specifically, they complaint that most old building lecture halls erected in the 60s and 80s are not contextually in harmony with the present existing structural development and natural environmental features. Consequently, they are not promoting the natural features of college environment. They also complained of

poorly designed building massing creating unpleasant building appearance, disharmony in structural formation, poor harvest of natural light and ventilation into lecture halls among others.

This development is worrisome and is the motivation behind this study. In the course of literature reviews for this study, it was discovered that there existed dearth of local literatures on building context and massing, especially concerning Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. Perhaps, is an indication that researchers might have not seen the necessity of researching in to these sensitive areas of building in public colleges of education in North Central, Nigeria. Therefore, there are existed gap of local literatures to fill, and the creating of awareness especially to the Federal and State Governments who are the owners of these colleges. The researcher equally wants to bring to the knowledge of potential researchers to see these areas as virgin areas of research. Thus, this study evaluated building context and massing and provided feedback and recommendations for possible improvements.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is Post Occupancy Evaluation of Building context and massing in Public Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of this study sought to determine;

- 1 The extent to which the building suits the context of the surrounding environment.
- 2 Extent of the successful use of concept of massing to subdivide buildings into identifiable parts.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1 To what extent have the building suits the context of the surrounding environment?
- 2 To what extent is the successful use of concept of massing to subdivide buildings into identifiable parts?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers and students on the extent to which the building suits the context of surrounding environment
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers and students on the extent of successful use of concept of massing to subdivide building into identifiable parts.

Literature Review

Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE)

Post occupancy evaluation is building assessment toolkit that seeks to identify major successes and failures of building performance and thereby proffer solutions for possible improvement. Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE) is an assessment toolkit designed with the main objective of investigating buildings in use in terms of users' comfort and satisfactions (Ene, 2015). Thus, POE employs interview, structured questionnaire, workshop, check list, and walkthrough and documentation, as well as modern age sophisticated scientific devices for information collection on building performance. The usually targeted groups of POE during data collection are the users and occasionally the professionals (architects, builders and others).

According to Faris (2017), Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE) tries to answer four broad questions that include; how is the building performing? Is it the intended performance levels? If not, how can it be improved upon? and How can the future building be improved? Thus, the feedback of POE conducted can add values to building assessed, improve future building design quality, quality of building materials and quality of lives of users. Therefore, buildings must be evaluated and improve upon to conform to users' needs and expectations (Izran, 2020).

Walker (2011) and Henry, Celen and Mine (2015) observed that most often, few POE studies carried out in educational environments in Nigeria have been on availability and maintainability of student's hostels facilities, ignoring some key aspects of building design elements that improve indoor environmental quality and other external built environmental factors that improve building and environmental appearance. Some of these building design elements are building context and massing.

Building Context

Building context is the environmental physical features of a defined building site. It is that architectural principle that requires that a new building erected should blend with the built and natural features of the environment it is sited. By this principle, it is expected that a new building erected should not stand tall in posture, but add values to already existing environmental features. Therefore, it is recommended that ideal infill building should conform to its surrounding natural and built environmental features such as aesthetic, topography of the area, the site history, architectural style of existing buildings, local culture of the area and other environmental features (Radha, 2018).

Basically, the environmental context of building site determines the choice of architectural style, building materials selection, construction method and site layout, which are very important in erecting quality building and the creation of an appealing environment. The principle of building context promotes continuity between the building and local history of a defined environment, and harmony with adjacent surrounding features.

Building Massing

Massing is architectural principle of composing and manipulating three-dimensional structural forms to form a unified coherent architectural configuration (Jacoby, 2016). In other word is the use of different shapes and sizes to form harmonious architectural unit or structure. Massing, if well-articulated brings about relative harmony in building height, width and length. It creates opportunity of maximizing landform, the harvest of natural light and ventilation into building indoor environment, provides pleasant appearance to building and surrounding environments, the forming of planned relationship between building parts and characteristics of the site, among others.

Research Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The area of study was North Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. This comprised of: Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Niger, Plateau and Nasarawa States. North Central, Nigeria is geographically located between Latitude $10^{\circ} 19' 60''$ N and Longitude $7^{\circ} 45' 0''$ E of the Prime Meridian, and boundaries with North East, North West, South East, South West and South-South, on Latitude and Longitude as shown in figure 1.

The population of the study was 933. This comprised of 13 Architects, 300 lecturers and 620 part II and III Students drawn from the 13 public colleges of education in North Central Nigeria (FRN, 2020). The sample of the

study was 420 respondents, 6 colleges of education and 3 states being 45% respectively. The instrument for data collection was a 14 items structured questionnaire titled “Post Occupancy Evaluation of Building Context and Massing Questionnaire (POEBCM)”. The questionnaire was divided into three sections, which consisted of Section A-C. Section “A” was designed to collect respondent’s personal data, section “B” consisted questions on building context while, section “C” contained research questions on building massing. The questionnaire numerical rating values was based on a seven-point rating scale with Very Unsatisfactory (VU=1); Unsatisfactory (U=2); Somewhat Unsatisfactory (SU=3); Somewhat satisfactory (SS=4); Satisfactory (S=5); Neither (N=6); and Very satisfactory (VS=7). The instrument was content and face validated by three experts from the department of technology education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi, Nigeria.

The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. The researcher administered the instrument to the respondents with the help of 6 research assistants. A total of 420 questionnaires were administered to the respondents and the 420 completed questionnaires were returned which represented 100% return. Descriptive statistical mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses. The choice of ANOVA was that, the study was designed to examine the potential differences among the three categories of respondents (Lecturer, architects and students).

Figure: 1. Map of North Central Geo-Political Zone of Nigeria Showing Area of Study.

Source: FRN, 2021.

Results

Research Question One

To what extent has the building suits the context of the surrounding environment?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on Building Suits the Context of the Surrounding Environment

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
1.	The college building suits the context of its surrounding environment.	420	2.20	0.40	Unsatisfactory
2.	The scale of the building suits the site it's sited upon.	420	6.27	1.36	Satisfactory
3.	The scale of the building suits the scale of the surrounding buildings.	420	5.83	1.81	Satisfactory
4.	The public and private relate well with one another.	420	6.61	0.96	Very satisfactory
5.	The land adjacent to the building fits harmoniously with the building.	420	6.01	1.72	Satisfactory
6.	The college building facilities and its intended uses fit well with the type and uses of adjacent buildings.	420	2.11	0.62	Unsatisfactory
7.	The appearance of the building fits in well with the building surrounding environment.	420	2.26	0.74	Unsatisfactory

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

Table 1 revealed the mean and standard deviation scores of the extent the building suits the context of the surrounding environment in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The data in table 1 showed that, the mean scores for the responses of respondents on items 2, 3, 4 and 5 were 6.27, 5.83, 6.61 and 6.01 with standard deviation scores of 1.36, 1.81, 0.96 and 1.72 respectively which is considered satisfactory. In the same vein, the mean scores for the responses of respondents on items 1, 6 and 7 were 2.20, 2.11 and 2.26, and with standard deviation scores of 0.40, 0.62 and 0.74 which are considered unsatisfactory. This implies that, the respondents indicated that the context of the surrounding environment such as the scale of the building site and building surroundings suit the context of the surrounding environment, and also the land adjacent to the building fits harmoniously with the building. Meanwhile, the building facilities, its fitness, intended uses and appearance didn't suit the context of the surrounding environment in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Research Question Two

To what extent is the successful use of concept of massing to subdivide buildings into identifiable parts?

Table 12: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on the Successful Use of Concept of Massing to Subdivide Buildings into Identifiable Parts.

S/N	Item	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Remarks
1.	Viewing from the outside, the building parts integrate well with each other to form pleasant appearance.	420	1.29	0.59	Very Unsatisfactory
2.	The subdivided parts of the building appear to have a function that is easy to identify.	420	4.30	1.04	Neither satisfactory
3.	It is clear what the various parts of the building means to visitors.	420	4.26	1.22	Neither satisfactory
4.	The various parts of the building are carefully planned in relation to one another and to the characteristics of the site.	420	2.26	0.70	Unsatisfactory
5.	The relationship between the buildings made them to be a unified structure.	420	2.23	0.61	Unsatisfactory
6.	The variation in the massing provides interest and variety.	420	2.11	0.51	Unsatisfactory
7.	The building components form harmonious appearance.	420	2.19	0.59	Unsatisfactory

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 2 revealed the mean and standard deviation scores of the extent of successful use of concept of massing to subdivide buildings into identifiable parts in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The data in table 2 showed that, the mean scores for the responses of respondents on items 1, 4, 5, 6 and 7 were 1.29, 2.26, 2.23, 2.11 and 2.19 with standard deviation scores of 1.59, 0.70, 0.61, 0.51 and 0.59 respectively, and are considered unsatisfactory. In the same vein, the mean scores for the responses of respondents on items 2 and 3 were 4.30 and 4.26 with standard deviation scores of 0.04 and 0.22 which are considered neither satisfactory. This implies that, the use of concept of massing to subdivide buildings into identifiable parts were unsatisfactory. By implication, viewing from the outside, the building parts did not integrate well with each other to form a pleasant appearance. Also the respondents indicated that the various parts of the building were not carefully planned in relation to one another. Similarly, it was found that the building components did not form harmonious appearance in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers and students on the extent to which the building suits the context of surrounding environment

Table 3: Result for ANOVA Analysis of Variance on Extent to which the Building Suits the Context of Surrounding Environment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.075	2	.537	1.557	.212
Within Groups	143.876	417	.345		
Total	144.951	419			

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

ANOVA analysis result in Table 3 revealed that, there is no significant variation among the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent which the building suits the context of surrounding environment in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria [$F_{2, 419} = 1.557, P > 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that, there is no significant variation in the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent which the building suits the context of surrounding environment in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference in the mean responses of architects, lecturers, and students on the extent which building performance indicators met their purposes in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria

Table 4: Result for Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Extent of successful Use of Concept of Massing to Subdivide Building into Identifiable Parts

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.304	2	.152	1.317	.269
Within Groups	48.116	417	.115		
Total	48.420	419			

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

ANOVA analysis result in Table 4 revealed that, there is no significant variation among the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent of successful use of concept of massing to subdivide building into identifiable parts in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria [$F_{2, 419} = 1.317, P > 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that, there is no significant variation in the mean responses of lecturers, students and architects on the extent of successful use of concept of massing to subdivide building into identifiable parts in public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study focused on post occupancy evaluation of building context and massing in public Colleges of Education in North-Central, Nigeria. The findings revealed that, the scale of the building suits the site it's sited upon and the surrounding buildings, and also the land adjacent to the buildings fits harmoniously with the buildings in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The findings also indicated that, the college building facilities did not suit the context of its surrounding environment, and the building and it intended uses did not fit well with the type and uses of adjacent buildings. Similarly, it was also found that the appearance of the building did not fit in well with the surrounding environment in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria. The finding of this study is in line with the finding of Thirumaran and Mohammed (2017) who revealed that, the conducive design guideline or framework for educational building did not fit in well in National Institution Technology, Tiruchioppalli University campus, India, thus recommended for improvement.

Similarly, the findings in question two revealed that, the subdivided parts of the buildings in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria appear to have a function that is easy to identify, and are also clear what the various parts of the building means to visitors. It was also found that, viewing from the outside, the building parts did not integrate well with one another to form pleasant appearance. It was further revealed that the various parts of the building were not carefully planned in relation to each another and to the characteristics of the site. Likewise, the relationship between the buildings did not make them to be a unified structure. The findings of this study is in line with the findings of Salah, Ammar and Daara (2014) who revealed that the challenges faced by building users in the University of Algeria were as result of poor building massing articulation and general design, thus it was recommended that the design should be improved upon to overcome the various challenges been faced by users.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that, the college buildings did not suit the context of their surrounding environments, and the building and it intended uses did not fit well with the type and uses of adjacent buildings. In the same vein, it was also found that the appearance of the building did not fit in well with the building surrounding environment. In the same vein, it is also evident from the findings of this study that, viewing from the outside, the building parts did not integrate well with each other to form pleasant appearance, and the various parts of the building are not carefully planned in relation to one another and to the characteristics of the site in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made:

1. Building context in terms of internal and external appearance, and intended uses fitness should be improved upon as to meet up with educational needs of this age in Public Colleges of Education in North Central, Nigeria.
2. The various parts of the building should be carefully redesigned and reconstructed to relate to one another to form a pleasant appearance unified structure.

3. The building components should be carefully redesign and possibly rebuild in order form harmonious appearance and also in relation to the characteristics of the site.

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